

HYDROPHILIC CAROTENOIDS FROM *CROCUS SATIVUS* L.: BIOCHEMICAL PROPERTIES, GEOGRAPHIC VARIATION, AND FUTURE INNOVATIONS

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Abstract. Carotenoids are essential bioactive compounds for human health, commonly found in yellow, orange, and red-pigmented plants. While most carotenoids are lipophilic and insoluble in water, this limits their application in certain pharmaceutical and food systems. However, the rare occurrence of naturally water-soluble, or hydrophilic, carotenoids in specific plant species presents a unique opportunity for broader bioavailability and formulation flexibility. Hydrophilic carotenoids such as crocin are notable for their potent antioxidant, antimicrobial, and anti-inflammatory properties, making them promising candidates for pharmaceutical development. This study investigates the biochemical characteristics and bioactivity of crocin and related carotenoids extracted from the stigmas of *Crocus sativus* L. cultivated in Iran, Turkey, and Kashmir. High-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) analysis revealed significant geographic variation, with Iranian saffron showing the highest crocin concentration ($11414.67 \pm 516.34 \mu\text{g/g DW}$). Antioxidant capacity was evaluated using the DPPH assay, while antimicrobial activity was tested via the disc diffusion method against *Staphylococcus epidermidis*. The results confirm crocin's efficacy as both an antioxidant ($IC_{50} = 283.918 \pm 3.934 \mu\text{g/mL}$) and an antimicrobial agent, with notable inhibition zones at concentrations of $100 \mu\text{g/mL}$. Given its bioactivity, crocin is proposed as a candidate active pharmaceutical ingredient (API) for therapeutic applications. In light of land availability and cultivation limitations, future research will explore *in vitro* culture and metabolic engineering approaches to enhance crocin production through biotechnological means. These findings position hydrophilic carotenoids from saffron as valuable natural resources with commercial and medical relevance.

Keywords. *Crocus sativus* L., crocin, hydrophilic carotenoids, bioactive compounds, natural pigments, geographic variation.